

STUDIES CONCERNING THE PRODUCTIVITY OF PERMANENT GRASSLANDS FROM CODRU-MOMA MOUNTAINS (WESTERN ROMANIAN CARPATHIANS)

T. MARUȘCA^{1,2}, C.Gh. PĂȘCUT²

¹ Research-Development Institute for Grasslands
Brasov, *maruscat@yahoo.com*

² University from Oradea, Gen. Magheru Str.,
No. 26, cod.410048, Oradea, *pascutcalin@yahoo.com*

* Corresponding author e-mail: *maruscat@yahoo.com*

Abstract

An important role in elaborating the pastoral arrangements and thus contribute to the sustainable management of the permanent grasslands is played by the outline of the grassland phytocenoses along with the evaluation of productivity (forage production and quality). Having at our disposal the phytocenological classification of the grasslands from Codru-Moma Mountains, their productivity was evaluated according to a new method, based on a floristic survey. The pre-mountain and mountain grasslands located between 300–900 m altitudes have an average production of 8.21 t/ha green mass production (GM) and a pastoral value (PV) of 47 (medium), with very big differences between the vegetation associations. The highest production of 18.3 t/ha GM and 85 PV is found in *As. Trifolio repenti-Lolietum* and the lowest of 0.7 t/ha GM and 7 PV in *As. Clinopodium – Pteridietum aquilini*. The final evaluation of the productivity expressed in cow's milk per hectare in the grazing season (160–175 days) highlighted the *Cynosurion* and *Phalaridion arundinacea* Alliances with 3300–3800 liters per hectare. The lowest milk productions of 200–700 liters per hectare were evaluated at the *Trifolium medii* and *Potentillo-Nardion* alliances. On average, the grasslands found in the study area showed to be quite valuable, ensuring a production of over 2000 liters of milk per hectare in an optimal grazing season.

Keywords: *mountain grasslands, green mass production, pastoral value, milk production.*

INTRODUCTION

Assessing the production and forage quality of a grassland has an important economic role both for the rational feeding of animals and in the sustainable management of this way of agricultural use. The classical methods for determining the production of grasslands require fencing grasslands areas in at least three repetitions for a specific type of grassland in order to protect it from grazing animals, then mowing, weighing the grass several times a year, sampling for chemical analysis and others.

Considering the difficulties concerning the location and guarding the research areas, as well as the high costs for harvesting and chemical analyzing of the grass, a new method for evaluating the productivity of grasslands based on floristic survey was developed (Marușca, 2019). The results of this more expeditious and easy to apply method are sufficiently accurate for the preparation of pastoral arrangements including the plans of measures required for improving and rational using of permanent grasslands.

The productivity of permanent grasslands located in several physical-geographical areas has been evaluated according to this method until present (Marușca 2021a, b; Marușca and Nicolin, 2020; Marușca et al., 2019, 2020 a, b, c, d, e; 2021 a, b).

This manuscript is a case study for the evaluation of the productivity of permanent grasslands located in the Codru-Moma Mountains (46°20'–46°41' north latitude; 22°06'–22°32' east latitude), which belong to the Western Carpathians.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The evaluation of the productivity of the mountain grasslands is based on the doctoral thesis “Flora and vegetation of the Codru-Moma Mountains” authored by Călin Gheorghe Pășcuț (2012), under the guidance of Prof. PhD. Petru Burescu from the University of Oradea.

The author of this research established the following grassland phytocenotaxones:

- Cl. PHRAGMITETEA AUSTRALIS**, Túxen et Preising 1942
Ord. *NASTURTIO-GLYCERIETALIA*, Pignatti 1953
Al. *Phalaridion arundinaceae*, Kopecky 1961
1. As. *Agrostetum gigantei*, Sanda et al. 1994
- Cl. MOLINIO-ARRHENATHERETEA**, R Túxen 1937
Ord. *ARRHENATHERETALIA*, R Túxen 1931
Al. *Cynosurion*, R Túxen 1947
2. As. *Festuco rubrae-Agrostetum capillaries*, Horvat 1951
3. As. *Trifolio repenti-Lolietum* Krippelová 1967, Resmeriță et Pop 1967
4. As. *Anthoxantho-Agrostietum capillaris*, Sillinger 1933
- Cl. NARDO-CALLUNETEA**, Preising 1949
Ord. *NARDETALIA*, Oberdorfer 1949
Al. *Potentillo-Nardion*, Simon 1959
5. As. *Festuco rubrae-Nardetum*, Csűrós et Resmeriță 1960
Al. *Genistion pillosae*, Duvigneaud 1942
6. As. *Festuco-Genistelletum*, Issler 1927
- Cl. FESTUCO-BROMETEA**, Br.-Bl et R Túxen in Br.-Bl. 1949
Ord. *BRACHYPODIO-CHRYSOPOGONETALIA*, (Horvatic 1958) Boșcaiu 1972
Al. *Danthonio-Brachypodium*, Boșcaiu 1972
7. As. *Festuco rubrae-Danthonietum*, Csűrós et al. 1968
Ord. *FESTUCETALIA VALESIIACAE*, Br.-Bl et R Túxen in Br.-Bl. 1949
Al. *Festucion valesiaca*, Klika 1931
8. As. *Agrostio-Festucetum valesiaca*, Borisavljević et al. 1955
9. As. *Medicagini-Festucetum valesiaca*, Wagner 1940
10. As. *Poterio-Festucetum valesiaca*, J. Danon 1964
Ord. *STIPIO PULCHERINNAE-FESTUCETALIA PALLENTIS*, I Pop 1968
Al. *Thymio comosi-Festucion rupicola*, Pop 1968
11. As. *Thymio comosi-Festucetum rupicola* (Csűrós et Gergely 1959) Pop et Hodișan 1985
- Cl. TRIFOLIO-GERANIETEA SANGUINEI**, Müller 1961
Ord. *ORIGANETALIA VULGARIS*, Th. Müller 1961
Al. *Trifolion medii*, Th. Müller 1961
12. As. *Clinopodio-Pteridietum aquilini*, Dihoru 1975

For statistical calculations, the abundance-dominance of the species assessed with marks from "+" to "5" after the Braun-Blanquet scale was transformed into participation percentages, respectively coverage. For each species in the survey, the forage value indices (F) were introduced after Kovacs (1979), Păcurar and Rotar (2014), Marușca (2019) and Păcurar (2020).

Indices for forage value (F):

- | | |
|--|---|
| 1 = toxic for animals and humans; | 2 = harmful for animal products; |
| 3 = harmful grassy carpet; | 4 = poor forage value (ballast); |
| 5 = medium forage value (ex F1); | 6 = average forage value (ex F2); |
| 7 = good forage value (ex F3); | 8 = very good forage value (ex F4); |
| 9 = excellent forage value (ex F5); | X = species with unknown forage value. |

In order to determine the pastoral value (PV) and the production of green forage (GM), we used the method proposed by Marușca (2019) and applied in the previous manuscripts submitted and published by this journal (Marușca et al. 2019; 2020a; 2021a), which we won't detail anymore.

Based on these data, the optimal animal loading or grazing capacity (GC) expressed in large cattle unit (UL) per hectare is further determined according to the formula:

$$GC \text{ (UL/ha)} = \frac{GM \text{ (kg/ha)}}{Rd \times Gd}$$

where: Rd = daily requirements for grass for 1 UL, 65 kg, respectively 50 kg + 15 kg (30% – season climatic fluctuations and unconsumed remains); Gd = number of grazing days (season).

The evaluation of the optimal load with animals was performed as follows:

Value UL/ha	Grassland assessment
0.01–0.20	Degraded (Degr.)
0.21–0.40	Very poor (VP)
0.41–0.60	Poor (P)
0.61–0.80	Mediocre (Med.)
0.81–1.20	Average (Av.)
1.21–1.60	Good (G)
1.61–2.00	Very good (VG)
Over 2.00	Excellent (Exc.)

A final synthetic indicator used for grassland productivity assessment is milk production in the grazing season per unit area (Marușca, 2001). On the average gap of 400–800 m alt. where the permanent grasslands from the Codru-Moma Mountains are located, a quantity of 4 kg of green forage was established in order to obtain a liter of cow's milk. The duration of the optimal grazing season is 175 days on the 400–600 m gap and 160 days on the 600–800 m gap, decreasing by 7.5 days for every 100 m altitude.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The permanent grasslands located in the Codru-Moma Mountains have a secondary origin after the deforestation of the primary forests in the immoral floor of the two-storey deciduous trees (Ciocârlan, 2009):

- I. Sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*) subfloor and sessile oak mixtures (300–600 m) forests;
- II. Beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) subfloor and beech mixed forests (600–900 m alt.). The stationary conditions of the 12 grassland associations are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. General data comprising the station and the phytodiversity of the permanent grassland plant species associations

No. crt.	Plant species associations	Altitude (m)	Exposure	Inclination (degree)	Releve (nr.)	Plant species	
						No.	%
1	<i>Agrostetum gigantei</i>	585–800	N, NV, NE	0–35	13	70	77
2	<i>Festuco rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris</i>	480–880	All	0–18	25	158	174
3	<i>Trifolio repenti-Lolietum</i>	380–430	Plan, E, SE	0–5	5	44	48
4	<i>Anthoxantho-Agrostietum capillaris</i>	300–620	All	0–18	13	106	116
5	<i>Festuco rubrae-Nardetum</i>	600–800	Pl, S, V, SV, N	0–25	9	54	59
6	<i>Festuco-Genistelletum</i>	550–780	All	5–20	9	60	66
7	<i>Festuco rubrae-Danthonietum</i>	500–660	V, SV	5–12	5	77	85
8	<i>Agrostio-Festucetum valesiaca</i>	580–800	S, SE, E, SV	5–15	9	118	130
9	<i>Medicagini-Festucetum valesiaca</i>	340–640	S, SE, SV	5–10	6	60	66
10	<i>Poterio-Festucetum valesiaca</i>	390–800	S, SV, SE,	5–40	16	116	127
11	<i>Thymio comosi-Festucetum rupicola</i>	510–800	Plan, S, SE,SV	0–25	13	143	157
12	<i>Clinopodio-Pteridietum aquilini</i>	450–800	All	5–20	11	85	93
TOTAL AVERAGE		300–880	-	0–40	134	91	100

The grasslands are located on flat or sloping terrain with different exposures, especially sunny and inclined by up to 40 degrees.

In the 134 surveys performed, an average of 91 plant species were found, with a very high phytodiversity. Most plant species, respectively 158 were recorded at *As. Festuco rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris*, followed by 143 species found in *As. Thymo comosi-Festucetum rupicola*.

The grasslands with degraded grassy carpet belonging to *As. Festuco rubrae-Nardetum* consists of 54 species comprising almost 3 times less species than *As. Festuco rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris*, from which they evolved due to irrational grazing. The production of green forage mass of the grassland associations is extremely varied, as influenced by the floristic composition (Table 2).

Table 2. The productivity of the grassland phytocoenoses located in the Codru-Moma Mountains

Phytocoenosis	Green mass production		Pastoral value		Productivity assessments
	t/ha	%	Indices	%	
Al. Phalaridion arundinaceae					
1. <i>Agrostetum gigantei</i>	15.26	186	61.9	131	Good
Al. Cynosurion					
2. <i>Festuco rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris</i>	11.41	139	64.3	136	Good
3. <i>Trifolio repenti-Lolietum</i>	18.30	223	85.0	180	Very good
4. <i>Anthoxantho-Agrostietum capillaris</i>	9.79	119	62.8	133	Good
Al. Potentillo-Nardion					
5. <i>Festuco rubrae-Nardetum</i>	2.66	32	18.7	40	Poor
Al. Genistion pillosae					
6. <i>Festuco-Genistelletum</i>	6.81	83	40.7	86	Mediocre
Al. Danthonio-Brachypodium					
7. <i>Festuco rubrae-Danthonietum</i>	10.97	134	57.4	121	Average
Al. Festucion valesiaca					
8. <i>Agrostio-Festucetum valesiaca</i>	6.65	81	47.8	101	Average
9. <i>Medicagini-Festucetum valesiaca</i>	5.06	62	48.4	102	Average
10. <i>Poterio-Festucetum valesiaca</i>	4.75	58	41.0	87	Average
Al. Thymio comosae-Festucion rupicolae					
11. <i>Thymio comosi-Festucetum rupicolae</i>	6.07	74	32.4	68	Mediocre
Al. Trifolion medii					
12. <i>Clinopodio-Pteridietum aquilini</i>	0.74	9	7.2	15	Very poor
Average	8.21	100	47.3	100	Average

Thus, the highest green forage production of (GM) was evaluated at As. *Trifolio repenti-Lolietum* with 18.3 t/ha and a pastoral value (PV) of 85, being appreciated as very good.

At the opposite pole are the grasslands invaded by the great fern, As. *Clinopodio-Pteridietum aquilini* with 0.74 t/ha GM and only 7.2 PV, considered very poor, degraded. Likewise, the grasslands invaded by the non-valuable species *Nardus stricta*, which belong to As. *Festuco rubrae-Nardetum*, have very low productivity with 2.66 t/ha GM and 18.7 PV. The rest of the associations have mediocre, medium and good productivity.

On average, the production of grassland associations is 8.21 t/ha GM with 47.3 PV, both productivity indicators being considered as medium.

In terms of optimal animal loading and milk production per hectare, it closely follows the green mass production recorded by the grassland phytocoenoses (Table 3).

Table 3. Evaluation of grazing season period, loading with animals and cow milk production recorded in the alliances (habitats) of permanent grasslands

No. crt.	Grassland alliances (habitats)	Grazing season period (days)	Loading with animals		Cow milk production	
			UL/ha	%	L/ha	%
1	<i>Phalaridion arundinaceae</i>	160	1.47	207	3,815	186
2	<i>Cynosurion</i>	175	1.16	163	3,285	160
3	<i>Potentillo-Nardion</i>	160	0.26	37	665	32
4	<i>Genistion pillosae</i>	165	0.63	89	1,700	83
5	<i>Danthonio-Brachypodium</i>	170	0.99	139	2,740	134
6	<i>Festucion valesiacae</i>	170	0.50	70	1,370	67
7	<i>Thymio comosae-Festucion rupicolae</i>	165	0.57	80	1,520	74
8	<i>Trifolion medii</i>	170	0.07	10	185	9
AVERAGE		160	0.71	100	2,050	100

This parameter of animal production, cow's milk, reaches an average of 2,050 liters per hectare of grassland with an optimal loading with animals of 0.71 UL / ha in an average season of 165 days of grazing. The weakest results were evaluated at the Alliance *Trifolion medii*, with almost 200 liters per hectare and the highest production of 3,815 liters/ha at Al. *Phalaridion arundinaceae*, followed by 3,285 L/ha at Al. *Cynosurion* with a higher spread in the studied grasslands. After a higher number of evaluations of the mountain grasslands based on floristic surveys, it will be possible to generalize the results on large areas such as the Eastern Carpathians on north and south, the Southern Carpathians on east and west and the Western Carpathians north (Apuseni) and south (Banat).

CONCLUSIONS

The permanent grasslands located in the Codru-Moma Mountains have a very high average phytodiversity of over 90 species in a phytosociological association.

The average production of green forage is estimated at 8.21 t/ha with an average index of 47 pastoral value, with very large differences between the grassland associations.

The evaluation of cow's milk production exceeds 2000 liters/hectare in an optimal season of 165 days of grazing with an average loading with animals of 0.7 UL/ha of permanent grassland.

REFERENCES

- Ciocârlan V. 2009. *Flora ilustrată a României*. „Ceres” Publishing House, Bucharest.
- Kovacs A.J. 1979. *Indicatorii biologici, ecologici și economici ai florei pajiștilor*. Redacția de propagandă tehnică agricolă Publishing House, Bucharest.
- Marușca T. 2001. *Elemente de gradientică și ecologie montană*. Transilvania University Publishing House, Brașov.

- Marușca T.** 2019. *Contributions to the evaluation of pasture productivity using the floristic releve.* Romanian Journal of Grassland and Forage crops, 19:33–47.
- Marușca T, Elena Taulescu, Roșca V, Bajenaru B, Memedemin D.** 2019. *Contributions to the evaluation of grassland productivity on the Macinului Mountains National Park.* Romanian Journal of Grassland and Forage Crops, 20:17–26.
- Marușca T, Nicolin AL.** 2020. *Contributions to the study of the impact of grassland phytocoenoses in the upper and middle Timiș river basin on forage and livestock production (Banat, Romania).* USAMVB “Regele Mihai I-al României”, Research Journal of Agricultural Science, 52 (1):159–166.
- Marușca T, Ionescu I, Elena Taulescu, Ioana Simion, Anamaria Malinas.** 2020a. *Contributions to the evaluation of the productivity of permanent grassland from North Oltenia.* Romanian Journal of Grassland and Forage Crops, 21:49–59.
- Marușca T, Arsene GG, Elena Taulescu.** 2020b. *Assessment of permanent grassland productivity in Poiana Ruscă Mountains (South-West Romanian Carpathians).* Annals of the Academy of Romanian Scientists Series Agriculture, Silviculture and Veterinary Medicine Sciences, 9(1):62–69.
- Marușca T, Oprea A, Memedemin D, Pop OG, Tibirnac MN, Maftai DI, Ioana Simion, Elena Taulescu.** 2020c. *Assessment of phytodiversity and productivity of steppic grasslands from ROSCI 0201 Podișul Nord-Dobrogean.* Danube Delta, 8:63–82.
- Marușca T, Dihoru G, Doniță N, Memedemin D, Pășcuț CG.** 2020d. *Contributions to the evaluation of the productivity of permanent grasslands from the Babadag Plateau (Dobrogea).* Annals of the University of Oradea, Fascicle: Environmental Protection, 35: 85–94.
- Marușca T, Ularu P, Gurean DM, Marcela Dragoș, Elena Taulescu.** 2020e. *Contributions to the grassland productivity evaluation in the Perșani Mountains.* Jurnalul de Montanologie, 13:23–32.
- Marușca T, Oprea A, Elena Taulescu, Marcela Dragoș.** 2021a. *Contributions to the grasslands productivity assessment in Tecuci Plain and Siret Lower Basin.* Romanian Journal of Grassland and Forage Crops, Cluj Napoca, 23:61–68.
- Marușca T, Danciu M, Gurean DM.** 2021b. *Contributions to the evaluation of grassland from South Baraolt Mountains in terms of productivity.* Annals of the Academy of Romanian Scientists Series Agriculture, Silviculture and Veterinary Medicine Sciences, 10(1):79–87.
- Marușca T.** 2021a. *Contribuții la evaluarea productivității ecologice a pajiștilor din Masivul Vlădeasa (Munții Apuseni).* Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences “Gheorghe Ionescu Șişesti”, ACTA Agricola Romanica, Field plant culture series, Tom 3, 3:38–44.
- Marușca T.** 2021b. *Contributions to the assessment of Natura 2000 Habitat productivity of mountain pastures in Padurea Craiului (Southern-Eastern Carpathians).* Romanian Journal of Grassland and Forage Crops, Cluj Napoca, 23:99–104.
- Păcurar F, Rotar I.** 2014. *Metode de studiu și interpretare a vegetației pajiștilor.* Risoprint Publishing House, Cluj-Napoca.
- Păcurar F.** 2020. *Specii indicator pentru evaluarea și elaborarea managementului sistemelor de pajiști cu înaltă valoare naturală – HNV.* Casa Cărții de Știință Publishing House, Cluj-Napoca.
- Pășcuț CG.** 2012. *Flora și vegetația Munților Codru-Moma.* PhD thesis, University of Oradea.